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ABOUT THE PROBLEM OF STRESS AND STRESS TOLERANCE OF STUDENTS

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Annotation: The problem of stress and stress tolerance in junior medical university students has been studied. As a result of the conducted research, it was found that 5.7 % of students have a high level of adaptation, 64.4 % – an average level, 26.9 % – a low level, 2.8 % – an extremely low level of adaptation to the educational and household environment. The main causes of stressful situations among junior medical university students in the course of their academic activities and personal life are revealed.

Keywords: stress, students, adaptation

О ПРОБЛЕМЕ СТРЕССА И СТРЕССОУСТОЙЧИВОСТИ СТУДЕНЧЕСКОЙ МОЛОДЕЖИ

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Аннотация: Изучена проблема стресса и стрессоустойчивости у студентов младших курсов медицинского ВУЗа. В результате проведенного исследования установлено, что 5,7 % студентов имеют высокий уровень адаптации, 64,4 % – средний уровень, 26,9 % – низкий уровень, 2,8 % – крайне низкий уровень адаптации к учебной и бытовой среде. Выявлены основные причины стрессовых ситуаций у студентов младших курсов медицинского ВУЗа в процессе их учебной деятельности и личной жизни.

Ключевые слова: стресс, студенты, адаптация

Relevance. Students experience high intellectual and emotional stress in the process of studying at the university. Currently, the student has great resources for development. However, young students have a number of individual psychological characteristics that can prevent them from fully solving this task. For many, moving to another city, new housing conditions, the need to independently provide themselves with living conditions and food, the difficulty with processing a large amount of information, lack of free time are companions of student life. Most students do not know how to fully control themselves in stressful situations in educational activities and in the household sphere. Among the most important problems faced by students is the problem of experiencing exam stress [1, 2].

Stress is a functional state of the body that occurs as a result of an external negative impact on its mental functions, nervous processes or the activity of peripheral organs.

The manifestations of stress are: memory impairment, decreased creativity, difficulty concentrating, anxiety, mood swings, feelings of depression and loneliness, health problems, poor or increased appetite, excessive or insufficient sleep and emotional manifestations (irritability, aggression) [3].

Stressors are factors that cause the development of a stress reaction.

Stress tolerance in students is a complex personality trait, which is characterized by the necessary adaptation of the student to the effects of external and internal factors in the process of educational activity.

Levels of stress resistance according to Hans Selye:

1. High level of stress resistance. A person remains calm under any circumstances, even those in which the majority will panic. By virtue of experience and self-improvement, such a person has learned to cope with stress in any form. It is much easier for such people to minimize the consequences of unpleasant events.

2. The average level of stress resistance. A person with an average level of stress tolerance is able to withstand problems and troubles, although after a certain time, but releases critical situations. He does not panic and is able to soberly assess the problem.

3. Low degree of stress resistance. This level is typical for anxious individuals with an increased emotional background. Such people perceive most stressful situations as posing a threat to their safety. In a stressful situation, reactions manifest themselves in the form of anxiety, mental and physical stress. Anxiety is accompanied by a violation of the ability to analyze, a low degree of concentration of attention. This level of stress resistance is dangerous due to the occurrence of various psychosomatic diseases.

4. Extremely low degree of stress resistance. In stressful situations, such people are unable to control themselves. Stress for such people affects all body systems. The body of people with an extremely low degree of stress resistance wears out 40 % faster than people who live in peace [4].

The purpose of the study. To study the problem of stress and stress tolerance in junior medical university students.

Materials and methods of research. Comparative-evaluative, analytical and evaluative methods were used in the work. An anonymous questionnaire was conducted aimed at obtaining information about the levels of stress resistance among students, the causes and methods of overcoming stress. The obtained data were processed statistically. The respondents were undergraduate students of the Medical University aged 17-20 years. The study was conducted at the beginning of the spring semester.

Results and their discussion. After the winter holidays, 5.7 % of students have a high level of stress tolerance and, consequently, good adaptive abilities; 64.4 % of students have an average level of stress tolerance; 26.9 % of students have a low level of stress tolerance; 2.8 %

of students have an extremely low level of stress tolerance, which indicates serious problems with adaptation and a "premorbid state".

By gender, the division into groups was as follows: among girls, 2.4 % have a high level of stress resistance, 68 % have an average level of stress resistance, 26 % have a low level of stress resistance, 3.7 % have a very low level of stress resistance. Among young men, 17 % have a high level of stress resistance, 50 % have an average level of stress resistance, 30 % have a low level of stress resistance, 0 % have a very low level of stress resistance.

Based on the survey data, it can be concluded that most of the students have an average level of stress tolerance. Young men turned out to be the most stress-resistant.

The most popular methods of dealing with stress were the following:

1) destructive ways of overcoming stress among students: delicious food is in the first place (71 %), aggression is in the second (16.3 %), smoking is in the third (12.5 %);

2) constructive ways to overcome stress among students: sleep/rest (41.3 %) and communication with friends and family (41.3 %) are in the first place, analysis of their actions (17.3 %) is in the second place.

It was revealed that the main causes of stressful situations in the educational activities of students were: final papers not delivered on time – 13.4 %, examination session – 71.1 %, heavy academic load – 11.5 %, lack of interest in the discipline – 2 %, disappointment in the future profession – 2 %.

It was found that the main causes of stressful situations in personal life were: illness or death of family members – 76.9 %; conflicts with classmates and close people – 3.8 %; relocation – 3.8 %; problems in relationships with a loved one – 11.5 %; health problems – 3.8 %.

It was shown that the most frequent manifestations of learning stress were poor sleep (67.3 %), a feeling of constant lack of time (10.5 %), increased fatigue (7.6 %). The least frequent manifestations of educational stress were – deterioration of health (3.8 %), violation of social contacts (3.8 %).

Conclusions. The results of the study found that 5.7 % of students have a high level of adaptation, 64.4 % have an average level, 26.9 % have a low level, 2.8 % have an extremely low level of adaptation to the educational and household environment. The main causes of stressful situations among junior medical university students in the course of their academic activities and personal life are revealed. Destructive and constructive ways of overcoming stressful situations are established. Based on the results of the research, personal recommendations were made to increase the stress resistance of each respondent.

Bibliography

- [1] Selye G. Stress without distress / G. Selye. – M.: Progress, 1992. 165 p.
- [2] Shcherbatykh Yu.V. Psychology of stress / Yu.V. Shcherbatykh. – M.: Academy, 2005. 250 p.
- [3] Zimatkina T.I. Environmental medicine: a workshop for students studying in the specialties 1-79 01 01 "General Medicine", 1-79 01 02 "Pediatrics" / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Aleksandrovich, G.D. Smirnova. – Grodno: GrGMU, 2020. 32 p.
- [4] Zimatkina T.I. Valeology: a textbook for students of higher education institutions in the specialty "Nursing" / T.I. Zimatkina, A.S. Alexandrovich. – Grodno: GrGMU, 2020. 296 p.

Список литературы

- [1] Селье Г. Стресс без дистресса / Г. Селье. – М.: Прогресс, 1992. 165 с.
- [2] Щербатых Ю.В. Психология стресса / Ю.В. Щербатых. – М.: Академия, 2005. 250 с.
- [3] Зиматкина Т.И. Экологическая медицина: практикум для студентов, обучающихся по специальностям 1-79 01 01 «Лечебное дело», 1-79 01 02 «Педиатрия» / Т.И. Зиматкина, А.С. Александрович, Г.Д. Смирнова. – Гродно: ГрГМУ, 2020. 32 с.

[4] Зиматкина Т.И. Валеология: учебное пособие для студентов учреждений высшего образования по специальности «Сестринское дело» / Т.И. Зиматкина, А.С. Александрович. – Гродно: ГрГМУ, 2020. 296 с.

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